

First record of *Anoplocerus luteus* (Fieber, 1861) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Israel

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Anoplocerus luteus* (Fieber, 1861) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Israel is reported. The distribution of the species is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Anoplocerus luteus*, first record, distribution, Israel, Mediterranean Region.

In the Mediterranean Region, *Anoplocerus luteus* (Fieber, 1861) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) has been reported from France (Corsica), Greece, Italy, Malta, Morocco, Spain, Tunisia and Türkiye, so far. Furthermore, the species was reported from Azerbaijan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan (Moulet et al., 2024; Aukema, 2025).

Herein, the first record of *A. luteus* in Israel is reported: On 17.05.2025, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was observed and photographed in the kibbutz Kfar Masaryk, located in northern Israel at the Mediterranean coast. Nine related photos were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Netanel, 2025).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Anoplocerus luteus* (Fieber, 1861), Kfar Masaryk, Israel, 17.05.2025. (Photo: Omer Netanel).

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